

ORGANIZING PROJECT WORK AND FORMING SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH SKILLS IN STUDENTS AND YOUNG PEOPLE

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Annotation

In this article, the issues of using project work, forming scientific-practical skills, independent work on oneself, and developing scientific-methodical recommendations that serve to increase the effectiveness of education of talented students are presented. On the basis of the experiences of developed foreign countries, the involvement of high school and academic lyceum students in scientific activities during small projects and the effective organization of small research works during the educational process are highlighted.

Key words: Project work, scientific research, gifted student, scientific outlook.

Based on the experiences conducted in educational institutions, it can be said that it is important to conduct small projects in connection with the formation of scientific and practical skills of students in the educational process. Involvement of students in project work allows to connect their theoretical knowledge with practice, brings them closer to production processes. In order for Uzbekistan to reach the level of the developed countries of the world in economic production, cultural and educational spheres, it is necessary to organize scientific activities among young people starting from schools and academic lyceums. This cannot be achieved without our students having a new scientific outlook. In the teaching of chemistry, it is not enough to study theoretical knowledge in depth, it is necessary to develop their talents and abilities, to involve students in scientific research, and to develop research skills and abilities. Development of effective forms, methods and means of implementing a technological approach to the process of intellectual and cultural development of students in the classroom and outside the classroom in the teaching of chemistry, foreign languages and Latin; it consists of developing scientific and theoretical proposals and recommendations based on the results of experiments and research on the intellectual and cultural development of students. In order to form scientific practical skills, students should be taught to

work in the Internet system, study data, analyze them, draw conclusions from the obtained data, and conduct small projects on the given topic. A student's acquisition of scientific and practical skills, assimilation of scientific knowledge, is of great importance in mastering the science of chemistry. As a result of this, students: - firstly, try to analyze and interpret the nature of processes and events occurring in nature;

- secondly, scientific activity develops the ability of independent thinking in a person; - thirdly, he will be aware of the scientific news happening in the world. It is necessary to explain to students that they should have intellectual potential and strive for innovation when giving students an understanding of scientific research. Carrying out project work develops creative thinking, initiative, independent thinking, and the ability to select the necessary from a lot of information. The purpose of students' participation in project work is to develop their inquisitiveness and creativity. It is necessary to acquaint students with existing life problems. In this case, the student is more interested in the solution of problems during the learning process and tries to learn more deeply the information he is interested in from the pages of the literature he is studying, the information related to the solution of this problem tries to get acquainted with more literature and sources to find information. This creates an opportunity for students to more thoroughly absorb information related to the solution of a certain problem. The main goal of educating talented students and working with them is to bring up unique talents who increase the scientific and creative potential of our country, to give them an opportunity to show and develop their natural abilities in a specific field of science. Gifted students are identified according to the level of development of their abilities by conducting psychological and pedagogical tests. The student's defense and discussion of the obtained results increases their interest in learning. From the obtained learning indicators, it is known that positive changes begin to be observed in students who have carried out project work: excellent mastery of subjects, increased interest in language learning, mutual support, such as the increase in the number of students who expressed their desire to participate in the competitions, the formation of aspirations to learn the cause of the problems they live in and have always followed, and they have a scientific worldview. There are also cases of critical use of literature information based on the information obtained by the students themselves and as a result of conducting research, which means that the involvement of students in project work is the basis for increasing their ability to think independently.

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